

Imidazole assisted generation of dioxovanadium(V) species incorporating a family of hydrazone ligands. Synthesis, characterization and reactivity

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Abstract : Methanolic solution of $[V^{IV}O(acac)_2]$ reacts with equivalent amount of benzoyl hydrazone of 2-hydroxyacetophenone and its 5-substituted derivatives (H_2L^{1-4} , general abbreviation H_2L) in presence of excess imidazole (im) to afford the $(imH)^+[VO_2(L)]^-$ (1-4) complexes. Complexes are diamagnetic and 1 : 1 electrolytic in nature. They exhibit catalytic activity in the aerial oxidation of L-ascorbic acid and undergo reversible protonation reaction. 8-Hydroxyquinoline (Hhq) converts these dioxo complexes to monooxo $[V^VO(L)(hq)]$ complexes.

Keywords : Dioxovanadium(V) complexes, hydrazone complexes, reactivity.

Introduction

Formation and stability of oxovanadium(V) species from its tetravalent precursor e.g. $[V^{IV}O(acac)_2]$ is ligands' basicity dependent¹⁻¹². Moreover, the generation and stability of any one of the three motifs in pentavalent state (viz. VO^{3+} , $V_2O_3^{4+}$ and VO_2^+), depends upon the nature of solvent as well as pH of the reaction medium. Normally, the complexes with VO^{3+} motif^{3-5,10} are formed in a hydroxylic medium (e.g. CH_3OH , C_2H_5OH etc.) while the complexes with $V_2O_3^{4+}$ are formed in a non-hydroxylic medium (e.g. acetone, acetonitrile, CH_2Cl_2 etc.)^{6,7}. The pH of the medium for the generation of these two motifs is either neutral or slightly acidic in nature. Generally, the complexes with VO_2^+ motif are formed in a hydroxylic medium^{1,8-11} having $pH > 7$. As a part of our program on the chemistry of oxovanadium(IV/V) complexes with a family of benzoyl hydrazone ligands, it has been found that the methanolic solution of equimolar amount of $[V^{IV}O(acac)_2]$ and the benzoyl hydrazone of either 2-hydroxyacetophenone or its 5-substituted derivatives (H_2L^{1-4} , general abbreviation H_2L) in presence of excess pyridine (py, $pK_a = 5.48$)¹³, the quaternary complexes⁴ of the type $[V^VO(L)(OCH_3)(py)]$ were formed while the similar reaction mixture in presence of excess monodentate alkyl amine base [e.g. ethyl amine ($pK_a = 10.64$), diethyl amine ($pK_a = 10.98$), triethyl amine ($pK_a = 10.75$) and piperidine ($pK_a = 11.12$) (general abbreviation, B)] afforded dioxovanadium(V) complexes¹ of

the type $BH^+[VO_2(L)]^-$. To the best of our knowledge, no work has been reported regarding the complexes formed by this family of benzoyl hydrazones in presence of excess imidazole (a relatively weak basic monodentate ligand $pK_a = 7.33$) having higher basicity than py but lower basicity than alkyl amines. Such type of complexes is very rare in the literature⁸. In this paper, we report the synthesis, characterization and some reactivity of the complexes formed by these hydrazone ligands in presence of excess imidazole. Such studies are important in connection with several catalytic¹⁴⁻²³ and medicinal activities²⁴⁻³⁷ of oxovanadium(V) complexes.

Experimental

Materials :

$[V^{IV}O(acac)_2]$ ³⁸ and the hydrazone ligands (H_2L^{1-4})³⁹ were prepared by the reported methods. Reagent grade solvents were dried and distilled prior to use. All other chemicals were reagent grade, obtained from commercial sources (Loba Chemical Company, India) and used without further purification. Spectroscopic grade solvents were used for spectral measurements.

Preparation of the metal complexes :

All the dioxovanadium(V) complexes containing the hydrazone ligands H_2L^{1-4} were synthesized by the same general method using $[V^{IV}O(acac)_2]$ as the starting material. Details are given for one representative case only.

$(imH)^+[VO_2(L^1)]^-$ (1) :

To a warm methanolic solution (20 ml) of H_2L^1 (0.254 g, 1 mmol) was added a methanolic solution (10 ml) of $[V^{IV}O(acac)_2]$ (0.265 g, 1 mmol) with stirring whereby a brown solution was obtained. To this brown solution a methanolic solution (10 ml) of imidazole (0.205 g, 3 mmol) was added with continuous stirring at room temperature. Immediately the colour of the solution changed to intense yellow. This mixture was then stirred for 1 h at $\sim 60^\circ C$ and then kept for slow evaporation at room temperature. After several days a golden yellow crystalline compound was obtained which was filtered followed by washing with methanol and dried over silica gel. Yield : 0.35 g (86%). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{17}N_4O_4V$: C, 53.47; H, 4.24; N, 13.86. Found : C, 53.32; H, 4.13; N, 13.75%; IR (KBr, ν_{max}/cm^{-1}) : 1591 (C=N_{azomethine}), 1357 (C-O_{phenolic}), 1251 (C-O_{enolate}), 1055 (N-N), 923, 892 (antisym and sym VO_2^+), 2949-3114 (N-H); Λ_M (DMF) = $52 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$; λ_{max} (DMSO)/nm : 386 ($\epsilon/dm^3 mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$ 10608), 320 (11210); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ/ppm) : 6.81 (2H, d, H-3, H-5, J 7.9 Hz), 7.31 (1H, t, H-4, J 7.9 Hz), 7.77 (1H, dd, H-6, J 7.7, 1.5 Hz), 2.86 (3H, s, $3 \times$ H-8), 8.05 (2H, d, H-11, H-15, J 6.5 Hz), 7.45-7.47 (3H, m, H-12, H-14, H-17), 7.63-7.65 (2H, m, H-13, H-18), 8.97 (1H, s, H-16), 4.54 (1H, brs, N-H).

$(imH)^+[VO_2(L^2)]^-$ (2) :

Yield : 0.34 g (81%). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{19}N_4O_4V$: C, 54.55; H, 4.58; N, 13.39. Found : C, 54.41; H, 4.41; N, 13.28%; IR (KBr, λ_{max}/cm^{-1}) : 1586 (C=N_{azomethine}), 1353 (C-O_{phenolic}), 1244 (C-O_{enolate}), 1040 (N-N), 955, 829 (antisym and sym VO_2^+), 2807-3157 (N-H); Λ_M (DMF) = $51 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$; λ_{max} (DMSO)/nm : 397 ($\epsilon/dm^3 mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$ 11231), 322 (13722); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ/ppm) : 6.70 (1H, d, H-3, J 8.1 Hz), 7.13 (1H, d, H-4, J 8.1 Hz), 2.29 (3H, s, 5- CH_3), 7.56 (1H, s, H-6), 2.85 (3H, s, $3 \times$ H-8), 8.04 (2H, d, H-11, H-15, J 6.9 Hz), 7.11-7.14 (3H, m, H-12, H-14, H-17), 7.62-7.64 (2H, m, H-13, H-18), 8.94 (1H, s, H-16), 3.80 (1H, brs, N-H).

$(imH)^+[VO_2(L^3)]^-$ (3) :

Yield : 0.31 g (71%). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{19}N_4O_5V$: C, 52.54; H, 4.41; N, 12.90. Found : C, 52.38; H, 4.32; N, 12.79%; IR (KBr, ν_{max}/cm^{-1}) : 1588 (C=N_{azomethine}), 1359 (C-O_{phenolic}), 1247 (C-O_{enolate}), 1042 (N-N), 948, 882 (antisym and sym VO_2^+), 2852-3155 (N-H); Λ_M (DMF) = $49 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$; λ_{max} (DMSO)/nm : 390 ($\epsilon/dm^3 mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$ 11726), 320 (12445); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ/ppm) : 6.68 (1H, d, H-3, J 8.0 Hz), 7.15 (1H, d, H-4, J 8.0 Hz), 3.78 (3H, s, 5-O CH_3), 7.48 (1H, s, H-6), 2.85 (3H, s, $3 \times$ H-8), 8.03 (2H, d, H-11, H-15, J 6.6 Hz), 7.07-7.10 (3H, m, H-12, H-14, H-17), 7.62-7.64 (2H, m, H-13, H-18), 3.52 (1H, brs, N-H).

$(imH)^+[VO_2(L^4)]^-$ (4) :

Yield : 0.34 g (77%). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{16}N_4O_4ClV$: C, 49.28; H, 3.68; N, 12.77. Found : C, 49.17; H, 3.60; N, 12.62%; IR (KBr, ν_{max}/cm^{-1}) : 1595 (C=N_{azomethine}), 1362 (C-O_{phenolic}), 1238 (C-O_{enolate}), 1059 (N-N), 941, 878 (antisym and sym VO_2^+), 2822-3074 (N-H); Λ_M (DMF) = $46 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$; λ_{max} (DMSO)/nm : 395 ($\epsilon/dm^3 mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$ 12071), 323 (13025); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ/ppm) : 6.82 (1H, d, H-3, J 8.6 Hz), 7.31 (1H, d, H-4), 7.45 (1H, d, H-6, J 0.7 Hz), 2.86 (3H, s, $3 \times$ H-8), 8.05 (2H, d, H-11, H-15, J 6.5 Hz), 7.47-7.49 (3H, m, H-12, H-14, H-17), 7.66-7.68 (2H, m, H-13, H-18), 4.47 (1H, brs, N-H).

Physical measurements :

Elemental analyses were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O analyzer. Electronic spectra (in DMSO) were recorded on a Hitachi U-3501 spectrophotometer and IR spectra (as KBr pellets) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 782 spectrophotometer. 1H NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO- d_6 on a Bruker AM 300L (300 MHz) superconducting FT NMR spectrophotometer. Conductivity measurements of all the complexes were performed at 298 K in DMF solution with the Systronics 304 digital conductivity meter. The EPR spectra (X-band) of the reduced species were recorded on a E-112 Century series Varian E-102 Microwave bridge spectrometer. Tetracyanoethane (tcne) ($g = 2.0027$) was used to calibrate the EPR spectra.

Results and discussion

With a view to synthesizing quaternary complexes of the type $[V^VO(L)(OCH_3)(im)]$ like $[V^VO(L)(OCH_3)(py)]^4$ complexes with imidazole (im, $pK_a = 7.33^{13}$, a monodentate N-donor ligand having higher basicity than pyridine but lower basicity than aliphatic alkyl amine bases viz. ethylamine, diethylamine, triethylamine and heterocyclic amine base e.g. piperidine) the methanolic solution of equimolar mixture of $[V^{IV}O(acac)_2]$ and H_2L (where H_2L is the general abbreviation of H_2L^{1-4} , Scheme 1) were allowed to react in presence of excess imidazole. It has been found that these reaction mixtures yielded the

Scheme 1

dioxovanadium(V) complexes of the type $\text{imH}^+[\text{VO}_2(\text{L})]^-$ (1-4). Thus instead of forming mixed-ligand complexes through coordination to the metal (as with pyridine⁴), imidazole with its relatively higher pK_a value provides the basic environment around the metal center thereby assisting in the generation of dioxovanadium(V) species. Considering aerial oxygen being the oxidizing agent the formation of these dioxo complexes may be represented as :

where Hacac is the acetylacetone.

Similar observation was reported previously⁸ with a different hydrazone ligand. Magnetic susceptibility measurement indicates that the complexes 1-4 are diamagnetic indicating the +V state (d^0 system) of the vanadium. Molar conductance values of these dioxovanadium(V) complexes (vide Experimental section) in dimethylformamide (DMF) support their 1 : 1 electrolytic nature^{40,41}.

IR spectra of the complexes :

The tridentate dinegative binding nature of these hydrazone ligands in the enol form is evident from the disappearance of three ligand characteristic bands³⁹ in the regions 1646–1651, 2924–2989 and 3215–3240 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$, $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ and $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ respectively and the

appearance of a new $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ enolate band in the 1238–1251 cm^{-1} region. The characteristic $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$ stretches are observed in the 1586–1595 cm^{-1} and 1040–1059 cm^{-1} region respectively. The shifting of the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ (azomethine) stretch towards the lower wave number from the free ligand³⁹ also supports the coordination of azomethine nitrogen^{1,3-11,39} to the metal. The appearance of the characteristic $\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$ band in the appreciably higher energy region is due to diminished repulsion between the lone pairs of adjacent nitrogen atoms upon coordination. The strong band in the 1353–1362 cm^{-1} region is associated with the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (phenolate)⁴² stretching.

In addition to these bands, complexes also exhibit two sharp bands in the 923–955 cm^{-1} and 829–892 cm^{-1} regions, attributed to antisymmetric and symmetric stretching respectively of VO_2^+ motif^{1,8-11}. Complexes 1-4 exhibit a number of bands in the 2807–3157 cm^{-1} region which are assigned to the N–H stretching. The presence of multiple band and the band width suggest that the N–H hydrogens are involved in hydrogen bonding^{1,43,44}. IR spectral data are collected in the experimental section.

¹H NMR spectra of the complexes :

¹H NMR spectral data of all the complexes are given in the Experimental section. The DMSO-*d*₆ solution of the ligands exhibits signals at $\delta \sim 11.00$ and ~ 13.00 ppm which are attributed respectively to NH and OH

protons³⁹. Absence of these signals in the ¹H NMR spectra of all the four complexes indicates that they are bonded to vanadium through deprotonation.

In spite of our best effort none of the complexes **1-4** were obtained as X-ray quality crystal but, the meridional binding nature of these hydrazone ligands with the VO₂⁺ species in presence of different alkyl amine bases have been established very recently¹. Based on this as well as IR and ¹H NMR spectral data, it is reasonable to assume their gross structure as designated in Fig. 1.

R	Complex
H	1
CH ₃	2
OCH ₃	3
Cl	4

Fig. 1. Probable structure of the complexes.

Electronic spectra of the complexes :

The electronic spectra of the complexes **1-4** were recorded in DMSO solution in the 300–800 nm region and the spectral data are given in the Experimental section. Complexes being of *d*⁰ system, no *d-d* transition band is expected in their electronic spectra. They exhibit two intense absorption bands : one in the 386–397 nm region, which is assigned to ligand-to-metal charge transfer transition (LMCT)^{1,8-11} and another in the 320–323 nm region attributed to ligand characteristic $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition band of C=N bond^{1,8-11}.

Conductivity of the complexes :

The conductivity of all the dioxovanadium(V) complexes have been measured in *N,N*-dimethylformamide

(DMF) solution at 298 K with a view to examine their electrolytic nature and their molar conductance have been found to be in the 46–52 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ region indicating their 1 : 1 electrolytic nature^{40,41}, supporting their molecular formulae. The molar conductance values of all the complexes are given in the Experimental section.

Study of reactivity of the complexes :

Reduction with L-ascorbic acid :

The catalytic activity of these VO₂⁺ complexes (**1-4**) in the aerial oxidation of L-ascorbic acid has been studied in either methanol or DMSO solution. In this catalytic process, at first the vanadium(V) species is reduced by the L-ascorbic acid to vanadium(IV) which is further oxidized by the aerial oxygen to the original dioxovanadium(V) species. The net reaction is the oxidation of L-ascorbic acid by atmospheric oxygen catalyzed by V^V. This reaction was monitored by ¹H NMR, EPR and electronic spectroscopy. These dioxovanadium(V) complexes are yellow in either DMSO or CH₃OH. However, on addition of L-ascorbic acid (in excess), the yellow colour immediately changed to deep green and the characteristic narrow proton signals of the coordinated ligand of each of the **1-4** complexes (Fig. 2, upper part) are converted to a broad signal (Fig. 2, lower part) which suggests that during the reaction, the [V^VO₂(L)]⁻ complexes are reduced to a corresponding paramagnetic V^{IV} species. The absence of narrow proton signals for the ligand strongly suggests that the ligand is still attached to the V-atom even after reduction. This green solution is EPR active and displays axial EPR spectra. The EPR parameters for the complex **1** are : $g_{||} = 1.943$; $g_{\perp} = 1.973$; $A_{||} = 170.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{cm}^{-1}$; $A_{\perp} = 60.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{cm}^{-1}$ and a representative EPR spectra is displayed in Fig. 3. An analysis of the EPR parameter data reveals the relationships : $g_{||} < g_{\perp}$ and $A_{||} \gg A_{\perp}$, which are characteristic of an axially compressed *d*_{xy}¹ configuration⁴⁵⁻⁴⁸.

The reversible nature of this catalytic process is best monitored by spectrophotometric study. The deep green solution obtained after the addition of L-ascorbic acid to the methanolic yellow solution of these VO₂⁺ complexes exhibit a new band in the visible region near 675 nm (Table 1) which is attributed to a *d-d* transition. After keeping the solution in the air for some time, the new

Fig. 2. ¹H NMR spectral curves of (imH)⁺[VO₂(L¹)]⁻ (1) in DMSO-*d*₆ solution before the addition of L-ascorbic acid (upper part) and after addition of L-ascorbic acid (in excess) (lower part).

band disappeared gradually (Fig. 4) and finally (after ~ 12 h) the initial spectrum was obtained indicating the re-oxidation of the reduced V^{IV}-complexes to the original VO₂⁺ complex.

Reaction of the complexes with HClO₄ :

An increase in the intensity of the UV band near 320 nm and a decrease in intensity with shifting of the *ca.* 380 nm band to *ca.* 390 nm were observed in the electronic

Fig. 3. X-band EPR spectra of (imH)⁺[VO₂(L¹)]⁻ (1) after reduction with L-ascorbic acid in DMSO solution at 77 K; tce = tetracyanoethene.

Table 1. Electronic spectral data (in the 400–800 nm region) of the complexes 1-4 in methanol solution at 298 K after addition of L-ascorbic acid

Complex	λ_{\max}/nm ($\epsilon/\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)
(imH) ⁺ [VO ₂ (L ¹)] ⁻ (1)	677 (388)
(imH) ⁺ [VO ₂ (L ²)] ⁻ (2)	680 (269)
(imH) ⁺ [VO ₂ (L ³)] ⁻ (3)	678 (302)
(imH) ⁺ [VO ₂ (L ⁴)] ⁻ (4)	673 (143)

Fig. 4. Electronic spectra (400–800 nm) of a $7.546 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ methanol solution of (1) : (a) before the addition of ascorbic acid, (b) 15 min after the addition of ascorbic acid, (c) 40 min after the addition of ascorbic acid, (d) 80 min after the addition of ascorbic acid and (e) 720 min after the addition of ascorbic acid.

spectra of these complexes in methanol when a methanolic solution of HClO₄ (dissolved in minimum amount of

methanol) was added dropwise to it (Fig. 5). This observation can be interpreted assuming the formation of com-

Fig. 5. Titration of (imH)⁺[VO₂(L¹)]⁻ (1) with a saturated solution of HClO₄ in methanol; the spectra were recorded after addition of 1-drop portion of methanol-HClO₄ to 10-ml of $\sim 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ solution of complex 1 in methanol.

plexes of the type [VO₂(HL)] and [VO(OH)(HL)]⁺ via the stepwise protonation of the uncoordinated imine-N and the equatorial oxo-oxygen (eq. 2)¹⁰. This protonation reaction is reversible as the original spectrum is re-obtained on the addition of methanolic solution of KOH.

The cationic part of the complex is omitted for clarity. Such type of reversibility is important in connection with the catalytic activity of vanadium-dependent halo-peroxidase.

Reaction of the complexes with 8-hydroxyquinoline (Hhq) :

On reaction with equimolar amount of 8-hydroxyquinoline (Hhq) in methanol, these dioxovanadium(V) complexes are converted to the [VO(L)(hq)] complexes³⁹ (confirmed from their analytical and various spectral data). The pH of the resulting solution is increased to ~ 11 indicating the formation of base in this reaction. So, the reaction may be represented as :

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